

Environmental Impact Assessment of the Industrial Zone of Shwe Pyi Thar Township

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Abstract

Air pollution has been aggravated by developments that typically occur as countries become industrialized: growing cities, increasing traffic, rapid economic development and industrialization, and higher levels of energy consumption. Air and water quality issues are becoming of greater concern to the society because of the negative effects to human beings and the environment. This research describes the results of air and water quality issues in Environmental Impact Assessment reports (EIA) prepared for industrialization projects in Shwe Pyi Thar Township. It can be concluded that more concern should also be given to the monitoring of other pollutants such as Ca, Fe, Si and Pb. Standard mitigation measures for the industrial projects should be determined.

Introduction

An environmental impact assessment is an assessment of the possible positive or negative impact that a proposed project (e.g., reservoir, wastewater, air pollution, energy consumptions, energy management, grid line system, etc.) may have on the environment considering the environmental, social and economic aspects. The International Association for Impact Assessment (IAIA) defines an environmental impact assessment ‘the process of identifying, predicting, evaluating and mitigating the biophysical, social, and other relevant effects of development proposals prior to major decisions being taken and commitments made^[1].’ Environmental impact assessment is divided into four steps: acquisition of information, analysis of information, communication of conclusions and selection of appropriate actions. The purpose of this research is to investigate the extent of operational air quality impacts and waste water from existing and future pollution sources associated with the Project. The impacts from industrials emission of air pollution and waste water are assessed based on the available reference data.

Air Quality Impact Assessment (AQIA) is a mechanism, which aids the efficient use of the air resource, where it is used, to identify, predict, and evaluate critical parameters and to identify the potential changes of air quality as a result of emissions from new proposed projects, to form a screening device for setting priorities in pollution control, to be used as a tool to test alternative project design at an early stage and aid the identification of the most suitable site in terms of benefit maximization and reduction of harmful effects (Parivesh newsletter: 2000) . Finally, to identify the type of industry this can be accommodated in an area while maintaining good air quality.

Scope and Approach of the Research

This research was conducted to evaluate the air and water issues being addressed in the approved preliminary assessment of industrials and infrastructures projects:

- To evaluate the adequacy of the monitoring carried out.
- To evaluate the adequacy of the prediction and identification of the impacts that expected to result due to development project activities.

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- To evaluate the appropriateness of the mitigation measures being proposed to curb air pollution problems.

The main assumption used for this research is that the impacts of the industrial and infrastructure are localized and of short duration. The air and water pollution impact that arises from the construction phase is mainly particulate matter and dust that may result from construction activities and gaseous pollutants mainly from the industrial emission of smoke (DEAT: 2006).

Research Area and Area's Meteorology

The proposed research area is located in the northwestern part of Yangon Division, between the town of Insein and the town of Hlaing Thar Yar. The area of the research region is approximately 39.38km² along the No. (4) highway road (see Figure-1 and 2). The proposed site is commonly referred to as Shwe Pyi Thar industrial zone (1,2,3,4), but 50% of the industrial zone is located in the Insein township. The research area is characterized by square and that is supported to the research work. The minimum requirements for air pollution modelling are knowledge of the wind speed, wind direction, atmospheric turbulence parameters, the ambient temperature, as well as the mixing height. The atmospheric boundary during the day is normally unstable, as a result of the sun's heating effect on the earth's surface.

The thickness of the mixing height depends strongly on solar radiation, amongst other parameters. This mixing layer gradually increases in height from sunrise, to reach a maximum at about five to six hours after sunrise. Cloudy conditions, surface and upper air temperatures also affect the final mixing height and its growth. The ground condition of the meteorological data of the research area is shown in Table (1). These data based on the humidity of 91%.

Figure 1. Industrial Zone (1) of Research Area

Figure 2. Industrial Zone (2,3,4) of the Research Area

Table (1) Meteorological data of the research area

Meteorological survey	Parameter
Wind speed	2mph (or) 3km/h
Wind direction (unstable)	NW, E,
Local temperature	Between 26°C and 30°C

Construction of the Dust Collector from Air

A dust collector is a system used to enhance the quality of air released from industrial and commercial processes by collecting dust and other impurities from air or gas. Designed to handle high-volume dust loads, a dust collector system consists of a blower, dust filter and a dust receptacle or dust removal system. It is distinguished from air cleaners, which use disposable filters to remove dust. Shape of the dust collector is circle and diameter of the collector is 6 inches. Dust collectors may be of single unit construction, or a collection of devices used to separate particulates matter from the process air. They are often used as an air pollution control device to maintain or improve air quality.

In this research, constructed the single unit dusts collector by using the electric fan, chemical filter research, 12V battery and 20W solar panel. The function of the electric fan or motor are supplies mechanical energy to move contaminated air from the dust –producing source to a dust collector. The function of the battery is supply the current to the fan and on the other hand storage the electricity from the solar panel. Dust from the air is deposit to the chemical filter paper and then collected the dust sample from the filter research day by day. The diameter of the filter is 5 inches. The Figure of the dust collector was shown in Figure (3).

Figure 3. The dust collector

Collection of the Dust Sample in the Industrial Zone

First, the dust must be captured on the filter paper. This is accomplished with devices such as capture hoods to catch dust at its source of origin. Many times, the machine producing the dust will have a port to which a dust can be directly attached. Second, the dust must be conveyed. This is done via a ditching system, properly sized and manifold to maintain a consistent minimum air velocity required to keep the dust in suspension for conveyance to the collection device. Finally, the dust is collected. This is done via a variety of means, depending on the application and the dust being handled.

Collection of the dust sample process is very difficult; because of the area of the research area is widely area and approximately 39.39km². In the research area located and constructed the concrete road, industries, market, and vehicles. And also some infrastructures are currently in working progress. So, in this research collected the dust sample especially in public areas (example: near road, park, school, etc.) by using the sample collector. The sample was collected in research area at every day during the September and October. The sample collection figure was shown in Figure (4) and (5). Small amount of sample dust got from the sample holder of sample collector in every day. Small amount of sample was shown in Figure (6). Finally, within 60 days, dust sample got the enough amount of the sample for elements concentration analysis by using the WDXRF machine. The sample was shown in Figure (7). The collected amount of the dust sample was shown in Table (2).

Table. (2) The collected amount of the dust sample

Date of the sample collection	Amount of the collected sample (g)
9.9.2017	12.36
16.9.2017	13.89
23.9.2017	11.56
30.9.2017	10.87
7.10.2017	12.09
14.10.2017	10.01
21.10.2017	11.28
28.10.2017	13.09

Figure 4. Sample Collection in Industrial Zone

Figure 5. Sample Collection in Industrial Zone

Figure 6. Small Amount of Sample for a day

Figure 7. Sample collected in Filter Research

Collection of the Wastewater Sample in Research Area

Wastewater collected and disposes of industry wastewater generated from industrial using, alcohol industrial, household and cleaning activities in industrial zone. Any structure with running water, such as a house or office, must be connected to one of the following wastewater disposal systems. But, there is no wastewater disposal systems in Shwe Pyi Thar industrial Zone which is situated besides the Hlaing (or) Yangon River. Two creeks are flow from Mingalardon Township and across the Shwe Pyi Thar industrial zone, then flowing to the Hlaing River. The wastewater from every industry in Shwe Pyi Thar industrial zone is flowing to the two creeks directly or indirectly ways, so the wastewater is going to the Hlaing River. Therefore, the wastewater sample is collected from the creeks for experiment of atomic absorption spectroscopy especially in lead (Pb) concentration. The creek of the industrial zone in Figure (8).

Impacts identification and prediction

Impacts identification and prediction are the most important component of EIA. Its importance lies in the fact that when properly executed this would suggest the type and extent of impact on man and environment that may be expected from a particular activity or substance. This information would also assist in deciding mitigation measures. Prediction should be based on the available environmental baseline of the project area. Such predictions are described in quantitative or qualitative terms. Considerations in impact prediction is based on the magnitude of impact, extend of impact, duration of impact, significance of impact. In this research, impact identification and predication is analyzed by using the significance of impact, which mean that, the predication is based on the result of WDXRF and AAS analysis [3].

Figure 8. Wastewater creek of the Shwe Pyi Thar industrial zone

Results and Discussion

In this research, the reference data is based on the air quality index of $PM_{2.5}$ (particulate matter). $PM_{2.5}$ is an air pollutant that is a concern for people's health when levels in air are high. $PM_{2.5}$ refer to tiny particles or droplets in the air that are two or one half of microns or less in width. Like inches, meter, and miles, a micron is a unit of measurement for distance. There are about 25000 microns in an inch. $PM_{2.5}$ was come from car, truck, industrial waste, road and burning of fuels. $PM_{2.5}$ is also produced by common indoor activities. (e.g. tobacco smoke, cooking with fire wood, oil lamp etc.). Particles in the $PM_{2.5}$ size range are able to travel deeply into the respiratory tract, reaching the lungs. Exposure to fine particles can cause short-term health effect eye, nose, throat and lung irritation, coughing, sneezing and shortness of breath. So, $PM_{2.5}$ of air quality index is high pollution in the environment (Welford R: 1996). The AAS result of the wastewater of the lead concentration was shown in Figure (9). The mass of the $PM_{2.5}$ is equal to the $15\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Therefore, the result of concentration value of the collected samples from WDXRF and AAS is nearly by $15\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, the air and water quality of the research region is high pollution. But, in opposite, the air quality is not pollution.

Laboratory : National Analytical Laboratory
 Instrument : Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS)
 Sample : Wastewater (J-484-2), Pegu University

No.	Element	Concentration(ppm)
1.	Lead (Pb)	ND

ND = Non Detected

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Figure 9. AAS result of the wastewater

Table (3) The element concentration result of the dust sample from WDXRF machine

Types of elements	Element Concentration	Weight (g)	Weight per Volume ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) per 60 days
Mg	0.79%	0.39	3.34
Al	5.30%	2.65	22.45
Si	11.60%	5.80	49.09
K	1.27%	0.64	5.37
Ca	16.67%	8.34	70.55
Fe	4.78%	2.39	20.23
Pb	5.21%	2.61	22.05
Total	45.62%	22.81	193.08

Conclusion

In this research, dust sample and wastewater from Shwe Pyi Thar Industrial has been collected by using the sample collector. The dust sample from sample collector was quantified by EDXRF spectrometer and wastewater was analyzed by atomic absorbing spectrometer. Lead (Pb) was not found to possess the concentration in the resulting of wastewater sample of the research area, so the lead (pb) toxicity cannot affect the environment. The elements concentration results of the collected dust samples from WDXRF machine and calculation is $193.08 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ within in 60 days. So, the daily amount of the concentration value is nearly $3.30 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and this amount is so far from $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no environmental impact in research area in daily, but in long time the concentration value is very high and above the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ level. So the longtime duration, this amount of level can be impact to the environment and also can be affected to people who live in research region. On the other hand, actually should to consider the weather condition of the research region. Because the dust can be flow in the rain and wind direction and finally deposit to the soil.

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